

Interview Guide

Anonymous

1 Introduction Interviewer/Project/Rules (5 minutes)

Note for interviewer: repeat the information within informed consent, make sure that the interviewee understands that everything is consensual and that they can revoke their information anytime.

- Interviewer, reason for interview series
- Rules
 - the interview is voluntary and can be broken off anytime
 - the interview can be retracted
 - please still don't communicate illegal activities
 - if accepted, the interview will be recorded, transcribed by hand through the interviewer. During transcription the interviewee and mentioned companies/people/etc will be anonymized. The interviewee receives a copy of the transcript and needs to acknowledge the transcript.
 - if a citation is extracted from the interview, the interviewee will be presented with the citation and asked for their explicit permission
 - discussion of the consent form

2 Background Interviewee (5 minutes)

Note to interviewer: this is used to “warm-up” the interviewee and gather some context information about what the interviewee is currently doing and how they ended up there.

- What are you currently working on? What is your job description or title
- How would you describe your primary working area?
- Experience:
 - How long have you been in your current position?
 - How long have you been working in IT security?
 - How long have you been working in IT?
 - What did your education look like? Did you have dedicated instructions/lectures about IT security?

3 Projects in general (5 minutes)

Note to interviewer: talk about the general structure of projects and problems that happen during this phase. If possible, try to get some information about the distinction between vulnerability scans, penetration-testing, red-teaming, etc.

- How does a typical project/assignment look like? What is a typical mission statement?
- do you work alone or within a team? If the latter, how is the team constituted?
- is stealthiness important for your work?
- What's the typical project duration?
 - working hours?
 - processing time?
 - how to you determine that a project is done?
 - can a project be canceled/paused before the originally established end-of-project? If so, why and how do you determine that the project must be paused.

4 Describing a typical project (10 minutes)

Note to interviewer: initially let the interviewee describe how projects typically look like. If time-permits, ask for the a recent project and maybe let the interviewee contrast those two.

- Please describe a generic typical project in your work of line
- Please describe your last project
- are there distinct project phases or testing areas?
- how is the distribution between manual and automated activities?
- are there some standards or norms that you orient your work upon?

5 Attack selection and knowledge base (15 minutes)

Note to interviewer: let the interviewee focus upon how they select areas of attack as well as attack vectors. If interviewees provide blurry answers, make sure to not push them.

- What are typical attacks that you employ during assignments?
- Which are attacks are often successful? which are tedious to employ?
- how do you know which attack vectors exists in the first place? How do keep up to date with the state of the art? Do you perform fundamental research? If so, please describe it.

- How do you pre-select potential attacks for projects? What's the role of intuition? Do you have a formalized process (checklists?)
- how do you select concrete attacks during assignments? Are there operations or attacks that you do not test? Why not?
- how do you determine if an attack was successful?
- which tools are you using? how and why?

6 Areas of security testing (10 minutes)

Note to interviewer: after detailing how attacks are selected, go back to “now that you told us how you select attacks, how do you know what attacks are even possible”?

- what areas exist? please detail them. (use areas already mentioned during the interview, otherwise show a print of PTES and ask for feedback)
- which areas are timeconsuming?
 - which kind of tools would help or are already helping?
 - could you automate work or is it important for your understanding of the tested subject?
 - why do you think that your wanted tooling does not exist yet? what problems and challenges could such a tool experience?
- which areas are hard to master? Which areas are (in your opinion) really hard for beginners to grasp?
- where could better tooling help? Imagine a perfect world, what tool is helping you most?

7 Final words

Note to interviewer: this is the opportunity to let the interviewee let of steam and maybe catch some (for us) unexpected answers. If the interviewee keeps on talking, remind them of their time commitment but otherwise let them talk and capture information.

- preconceptions: what is a common preconception or wrong idea about penetration testing?
- What is most often understood when it comes to pen-testing?
- anything else that you want to add about pen-testing? Or what you often think about?